

CARLEMAN'S INEQUALITY OVER PRIME NUMBERS

Christian Axler

*Institute of Mathematics, Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf, Düsseldorf,
Germany*

christian.axler@hhu.de

Mehdi Hassani

Department of Mathematics, University of Zanjan, Zanjan, Iran

mehdi.hassani@znu.ac.ir

Received: 6/30/20, Revised: 1/29/21, Accepted: 4/22/21, Published: 5/4/21

Abstract

Motivated by studying Carleman's inequality over the prime numbers and over the reciprocal of the prime numbers, we consider the sequences $\{C_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ with general term $C_n = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n (p_1 \cdots p_k)^{1/k}}{\sum_{k=1}^n p_k}$ and $\{C'_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ defined similarly by replacing the numbers p_k by $1/p_k$ in C_n . Based on the recently obtained results concerning the arithmetic and geometric means of the prime numbers, we obtain asymptotic expansions and also explicit bounds for the sequences C_n and C'_n .

1. Introduction

For positive real numbers a_1, \dots, a_n , Carleman's inequality [6, 11] asserts that

$$\sum_{k=1}^n (a_1 \cdots a_k)^{\frac{1}{k}} \leq e \sum_{k=1}^n a_k. \quad (1.1)$$

The constant e in the inequality is the best possible, that is, the inequality does not always hold if e is replaced by a smaller number. However, this constant can be improved for some particular sequences $\{a_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$. In this paper we study this possibility for sequences of prime numbers and their reciprocals. As usual, let p_k denotes the k th prime number. We define the sequences $\{C_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ and $\{C'_n\}_{n=1}^{\infty}$ respectively by

$$C_n = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n (p_1 \cdots p_k)^{\frac{1}{k}}}{\sum_{k=1}^n p_k}, \quad \text{and} \quad C'_n = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n \left(\frac{1}{p_1} \cdots \frac{1}{p_k}\right)^{\frac{1}{k}}}{\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{p_k}}.$$

We denote by A_n and G_n the arithmetic and geometric means of the prime numbers p_1, \dots, p_n , respectively. It is known [13] that

$$A_n = \frac{p_n}{2} + O(n), \quad \text{and} \quad G_n = \frac{p_n}{e} + O(n).$$

Also, we write $B_n = \sum_{k=1}^n p_k^{-1}$, for which we have $B_n = \log \log n + O(1)$. These approximations and the prime number theorem in the form $p_n \sim n \log n$ as $n \rightarrow \infty$ imply that

$$C_n = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n G_k}{nA_n} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n (p_k + O(k))}{enA_n} = \frac{nA_n + O(n^2)}{enA_n} = \frac{1}{e} + O\left(\frac{1}{\log n}\right). \quad (1.2)$$

Hence, the constant e of Carleman’s inequality over prime numbers is not the best possible. In our first result, we obtain a more precise asymptotic formula of C_n compared with Equation (1.2).

Theorem 1. *As $n \rightarrow \infty$, we have*

$$C_n = \frac{1}{e} - \frac{1}{e \log n} + \frac{\log \log n - 3}{e \log^2 n} + O\left(\frac{(\log \log n)^2}{\log^3 n}\right).$$

Based on some explicit bounds concerning A_n and G_n in [13], and the n th prime number p_n in [14], recently the second author [12] showed that the inequalities

$$\frac{1}{e} - \frac{4}{\log n} < C_n < \frac{1}{e} + \frac{4}{\log n} \quad (1.3)$$

hold for every integer $n \geq 2$. Our first goal is to improve the inequalities given in Equation (1.3) in the direction of Theorem 1. In order to do this we use some results of [4] to get the following lower and upper bound for C_n .

Theorem 2. *We have*

$$\frac{1}{e} - \frac{1}{e \log n} + \frac{\log \log n - 5.485}{e \log^2 n} < C_n < \frac{1}{e} - \frac{1}{e \log n} + \frac{\log \log n - 0.345}{e \log^2 n},$$

where the left-hand side inequality holds for every integer $n \geq 2$ and the right-hand side inequality is valid for every integer $n \geq 55$.

To study Carleman’s inequality over the reciprocal of the prime numbers, first we observe that Equation (1.1) asserts that

$$C'_n \leq e$$

for every positive integer n . Considering the approximations $G_n = p_n/e + O(n)$ and $p_n \sim n \log n$, we get $G_n^{-1} = e/p_n + O(1/n \log^2 n)$. Hence,

$$C'_n = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n G_k^{-1}}{B_n} = \frac{eB_n + O(1)}{B_n} = e + O\left(\frac{1}{\log \log n}\right).$$

Thus, the constant e in Equation (1.1) is the best possible for the sequence $\{C'_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$. We give the following explicit estimates for this sequence.

Theorem 3. *We have*

$$e - \frac{1.14951}{\log \log n} < C'_n < e - \frac{0.71884}{\log \log n}, \tag{1.4}$$

where the left-hand side inequality holds for every integer $n \geq 4$ and the right-hand side inequality is valid for every integer $n \geq 6$.

Finally, we mention that computations running over the values of C_n and C'_n lead us to formulate the following conjecture.

Conjecture 1. The sequence $\{C_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ is strictly increasing for $n \geq 298$. Also, the sequence $\{C'_n\}_{n=1}^\infty$ is strictly increasing for $n \geq 1$.

2. Proof of Theorem 1

In the following proof of Theorem 1, we use some recent asymptotic results, due to the first author, concerning the sum of the first n prime numbers and the sums

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{p_k}{\log^j p_k},$$

where $j \in \{1, 2, 3\}$.

Proof of Theorem 1. By [5, Theorem 1.4], we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n p_k = \frac{n^2}{2} \left(\log n + \log_2 n - \frac{3}{2} + \frac{\log_2 n - \frac{5}{2}}{\log n} - \frac{(\log_2 n)^2 - 7 \log_2 n + \frac{29}{2}}{2 \log^2 n} + s(n) \right),$$

where $\log_2 x = \log \log x$ and

$$s(n) = O \left(\frac{(\log_2 n)^3}{\log^3 n} \right).$$

Further, we use the power series for $\exp(x)$ to obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \exp \left(\frac{1}{\log p_k} + \frac{3}{\log^2 p_k} + \frac{13}{\log^3 p_k} \right) \\ = 1 + \frac{1}{\log p_k} + \frac{7}{2 \log^2 p_k} + \frac{97}{6 \log^3 p_k} + O \left(\frac{1}{\log^4 p_k} \right). \end{aligned}$$

If we combine this with [4, Proposition 2.5], we get

$$eG_k = p_k \left(1 - \frac{1}{\log p_k} - \frac{5}{2 \log^2 p_k} - \frac{61}{6 \log^3 p_k} \right) + O \left(\frac{p_k}{\log^4 p_k} \right).$$

Hence

$$\begin{aligned} (eC_n - 1) \sum_{k=1}^n p_k &= - \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{p_k}{\log p_k} - \frac{5}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{p_k}{\log^2 p_k} - \frac{61}{6} \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{p_k}{\log^3 p_k} + O\left(\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{p_k}{\log^4 p_k}\right). \end{aligned}$$

Now we use the asymptotic expansions obtained in [3, p. 9] to see that

$$(eC_n - 1) \sum_{k=1}^n p_k = \frac{n^2}{2} \left(-1 - \frac{3}{2 \log n} + \frac{18 \log_2 n - 89}{12 \log^2 n} + r(n) \right),$$

where

$$r(n) = O\left(\frac{(\log_2 n)^2}{\log^3 n}\right).$$

It follows that

$$eC_n - 1 = \frac{-1 - \frac{3}{2 \log n} + \frac{18 \log_2 n - 89}{12 \log^2 n} + r(n)}{\log n + \log_2 n - \frac{3}{2} + \frac{\log_2 n - \frac{5}{2}}{\log n} - \frac{(\log_2 n)^2 - 7 \log_2 n + \frac{29}{2}}{2 \log^2 n} + s(n)}.$$

A straightforward but exhausting calculation shows that

$$eC_n - 1 = -\frac{1}{\log n} + \frac{\log \log n - 3}{\log^2 n} + O\left(\frac{(\log \log n)^2}{\log^3 n}\right).$$

This completes the proof. □

3. Proof of Theorem 2

In order to prove Theorem 2, we first note the following estimates for the sum of the first n prime numbers. The first one is due to Dusart [8, Lemme 1.7] and the second one due to the first author [5, Corollary 9.1].

Lemma 1 ([8, 5]). *For every integer $n \geq 305\,494$, we have*

$$\sum_{k=1}^n p_k > \frac{n^2}{2} \left(\log n + \log \log n - \frac{3}{2} \right), \tag{3.1}$$

and for every integer $n \geq 115\,149$, we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n p_k < \frac{n^2}{2} \left(\log n + \log \log n - \frac{3}{2} + \frac{\log \log n - 5/2}{\log n} \right).$$

In order to find the explicit estimates for C_n stated in Theorem 2, we also note the following identities concerning the sums

$$\sum_{p \leq x} \frac{1}{p \log p}, \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{p \leq x} \frac{1}{p \log^2 p}.$$

Lemma 2. *For every $x \geq 2$, we have*

$$\sum_{p \leq x} \frac{1}{p \log p} = \frac{\pi(x)}{x \log x} + \int_2^x \pi(t) \left(\frac{1}{t^2 \log t} + \frac{1}{t^2 \log^2 t} \right) dt, \quad (3.2)$$

and

$$\sum_{p \leq x} \frac{1}{p \log^2 p} = \frac{\pi(x)}{x \log^2 x} + \int_2^x \pi(t) \left(\frac{1}{t^2 \log^2 t} + \frac{2}{t^2 \log^3 t} \right) dt. \quad (3.3)$$

Proof. We set $y = 3/2$, $g(t) = 1/(t \log t)$, and $a(n) = \mathbf{1}_{\mathbb{P}}(n)$ in [1, Theorem 4.2] to obtain the first identity. In order to prove Equation (3.3), we set $y = 3/2$, $g(t) = 1/(t \log^2 t)$, and $a(n) = \mathbf{1}_{\mathbb{P}}(n)$ in [1, Theorem 4.2]. \square

Remark 1. The prime number theorem implies that the series

$$\sum_{p \in \mathbb{P}} \frac{1}{p \log p}, \quad \text{and} \quad \sum_{p \in \mathbb{P}} \frac{1}{p \log^2 p},$$

both converge. More precisely, Cohen [7, p. 6] showed that

$$\sum_{p \in \mathbb{P}} \frac{1}{p \log p} = 1.6366163233512608685696580039218636711 \dots \quad (3.4)$$

Further, Cohen used the method investigated in [7] to compute

$$\sum_{p \in \mathbb{P}} \frac{1}{p \log^2 p} = 1.5209704399395008634614286286155795220 \dots \quad (3.5)$$

In the following proof of Theorem 2, we use Lemma 1 and an upper bound for the logarithmic integral $\text{li}(x)$ which is defined for $x > 1$ as

$$\text{li}(x) = \int_0^x \frac{dt}{\log t} = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0^+} \left\{ \int_0^{1-\varepsilon} \frac{dt}{\log t} + \int_{1+\varepsilon}^x \frac{dt}{\log t} \right\}.$$

Proof of Theorem 2. First we show that the inequality

$$C_n > \frac{1}{e} - \frac{1}{e \log n} + \frac{\log \log n - 5.485}{e \log^2 n}$$

holds for every integer $n \geq 2$. Let $n_0 = 400765$ and consider first the case where $n \geq n_0$. Using [4, Corollary 5.7], we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k > G_1 + G_2 + \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^n p_k - \frac{2}{e} - \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^n k - \frac{3.74}{e} \sum_{k=3}^n \frac{k}{\log p_k}.$$

Since $G_1 + G_2 > 2/e$ and $\log p_k > \log k$, we get

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k > \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^n p_k - \frac{n^2}{2e} - \frac{n}{2e} - \frac{3.74}{e} \sum_{k=3}^n \frac{k}{\log k}. \tag{3.6}$$

Note that the function $x/\log x$ is increasing for every $x \geq e$. We combine this with [8, Lemme 1.6] to get

$$\sum_{k=3}^n \frac{k}{\log k} \leq \int_3^{n+1} \frac{x}{\log x} dx = \text{li}((n+1)^2) - \text{li}(9).$$

By the mean value theorem, there exists a real number $\xi \in (n^2, (n+1)^2)$ such that $\text{li}((n+1)^2) - \text{li}(n^2) = (2n+1)/\log \xi$. Thus, we obtain $\text{li}((n+1)^2) - \text{li}(n^2) < (n+1/2)/\log n$ for any $n > 1$, and so

$$\sum_{k=3}^n \frac{k}{\log k} \leq \int_3^{n+1} \frac{x}{\log x} dx < \text{li}(n^2) - \text{li}(9) + \frac{n}{\log n} + \frac{1}{2 \log n}.$$

Since $\text{li}(9) > 1/(2 \log n)$, we obtain

$$\sum_{k=3}^n \frac{k}{\log k} < \text{li}(n^2) + \frac{n}{\log n}. \tag{3.7}$$

Applying this inequality to Equation (3.6), we see that

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k > \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^n p_k - \frac{n^2}{2e} - \frac{n}{2e} - \frac{3.74}{e} \left(\text{li}(n^2) + \frac{n}{\log n} \right).$$

Now we use the fact that $\text{li}(x) < x/\log x + 1.09x/\log^2 x$ for every $x \geq n_0^2$ to obtain the inequality

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k > \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^n p_k - \frac{n^2}{2e} - \frac{n}{2e} - \frac{3.74n^2}{2e \log n} - \frac{1.01915n^2}{e \log^2 n} - \frac{3.74n}{e \log n}.$$

Since $C_n = \sum_{k=1}^n G_k / \sum_{k=1}^n p_k$, we can use Equation (3.1) to get

$$C_n > \frac{1}{e} - \frac{1}{e(\log n + \log \log n - 3/2)} - \frac{1}{en \log n} - \frac{3.74}{e \log^2 n} - \frac{2.0383}{e \log^3 n} - \frac{7.48}{en \log^2 n}. \tag{3.8}$$

Note that

$$-\frac{1}{\log n + \log \log n - \frac{3}{2}} \geq -\frac{1}{\log n} + \frac{\log \log n - \frac{3}{2}}{\log^2 n} - \frac{(\log \log n - \frac{3}{2})^2}{\log^3 n}.$$

Applying this inequality to Equation (3.8), we see that

$$C_n > \frac{1}{e} - \frac{1}{e \log n} + \frac{\log \log n - 5.24}{e \log^2 n} - \frac{(\log \log n - 3/2)^2 + 2.0383}{e \log^3 n} - \frac{1}{en \log n} - \frac{7.48}{en \log^2 n}. \tag{3.9}$$

Finally, we apply the inequality $0.245 \geq ((\log \log x - 3/2)^2 + 2.0383)/\log x + (\log x + 7.48)/x$, which holds for every $x \geq n_0$, to Equation (3.9) and get the required inequality for every integer $n \geq n_0$. A computer check for smaller values of n completes the proof.

Next, we prove that the inequality

$$C_n < \frac{1}{e} - \frac{1}{e \log n} + \frac{\log \log n - 0.345}{e \log^2 n}$$

is valid for every integer $n \geq 55$. First, we set $n_1 = 387572$ and consider the case where $n \geq n_1$. Using [4, Corollary 5.4] and a computer, we have

$$G_k < \frac{p_k}{e} - \frac{k}{e} + \frac{1.1k}{e \log p_k}$$

for every integer $k \geq 47$. A direct computation shows that

$$\sum_{k=1}^{46} G_k - \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^{46} p_k + \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^{46} k - \frac{1.1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^{46} \frac{k}{\log p_k} \leq 28.602$$

and it follows that

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k < 28.602 + \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^n p_k - \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^n k + \frac{1.1}{e} \left(\frac{1}{\log 2} + \frac{2}{\log 3} + \sum_{k=3}^n \frac{k}{\log k} \right).$$

Now we can use Equation (3.7) to get

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k < 28.602 - \frac{n}{2e} + \frac{1.1n}{e \log n} + \frac{1.1}{e \log 2} + \frac{2.2}{e \log 3} + \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^n p_k - \frac{n^2}{2e} + \frac{1.1}{e} \text{li}(n^2).$$

We have $x/(2e) \geq 28.602 + 1.1x/(e \log x) + 1.1/(e \log 2) + 2.2/(e \log 3)$ for any $x \geq 269$. Hence

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k < \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^n p_k - \frac{n^2}{2e} + \frac{1.1}{e} \text{li}(n^2).$$

We apply the inequality $\text{li}(x) < 1.05x/\log x$, which holds for every $x \geq n_1^2$, to obtain

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k < \frac{1}{e} \sum_{k=1}^n p_k - \frac{n^2}{2e} + \frac{1.155n^2}{2e \log n}.$$

Now we use the definition of C_n and the inequalities stated in Lemma 1 to get

$$C_n < \frac{1}{e} - \frac{1}{e(\log n + \log \log n - \frac{3}{2} + \frac{\log \log n - \frac{5}{2}}{\log n})} + \frac{1.155}{e \log n (\log n + \log \log n - \frac{3}{2})}.$$

Since $n \geq n_1 > \exp(\exp(2.5))$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} -\frac{1}{\log n + \log \log n - \frac{3}{2} + \frac{\log \log n - \frac{5}{2}}{\log n}} &< \\ &-\frac{1}{\log n} + \frac{\log \log n - \frac{3}{2}}{\log^2 n} + \frac{\log \log n - \frac{5}{2}}{\log^2 n (\log n + \log \log n - \frac{3}{2})}. \end{aligned}$$

Furthermore, the identity

$$\frac{1.155}{\log n (\log n + \log \log n - \frac{3}{2})} = \frac{1.155}{\log^2 n} - \frac{1.155(\log \log n - \frac{3}{2})}{\log^2 n (\log n + \log \log n - \frac{3}{2})}$$

holds. So we get

$$C_n < \frac{1}{e} - \frac{1}{e \log n} + \frac{\log \log n - 0.345}{e \log^2 n} + r_n,$$

where

$$r_n = -\frac{0.155 \log \log n + 0.7675}{e \log^2 n (\log n + \log \log n - \frac{3}{2})} < 0.$$

This implies the desired result for every integer $n \geq n_1$. For the remaining cases of n we use a computer. This completes the proof. \square

We get the following two corollaries.

Corollary 1. *For every integer $n \geq 43$, we have*

$$C_n < \frac{1}{e} - \frac{1}{e \log n} + \frac{\log \log n}{e \log^2 n}.$$

Proof. If $n \geq 55$, this is a consequence of Theorem 2. We conclude by direct computation. \square

Corollary 2. *For every integer $n \geq 14$, we have*

$$C_n < \frac{1}{e}.$$

Proof. From Corollary 1 follows that the required inequality holds for every integer $n \geq 43$. A computer check for smaller values of n completes the proof. \square

4. Proof of Theorem 3

We use Lemma 2 and the identities given in Equation (3.4) and Equation (3.5) combined with an explicit lower bound for the prime counting function $\pi(x)$ due to Dusart [10] to give the following proof of Theorem 3.

Proof of Theorem 3. We start with the proof of the left-hand side inequality of Equation (1.4) and first consider the case where $n \geq r = 8597$. Using [4, Proposition 5.1], we get

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k^{-1} > \sum_{k=1}^{r-1} G_k^{-1} + e \sum_{k=r}^n \frac{\exp\left(\frac{1}{\log p_k} + \frac{2.7}{\log^2 p_k}\right)}{p_k}.$$

Now we apply the inequality $e^x \geq 1 + x$, which holds for every $x \in \mathbb{R}$, to obtain

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k^{-1} > \delta_0 + e \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{p_k} + e \sum_{k=r}^n \frac{1}{p_k \log p_k} + 2.7e \sum_{k=r}^n \frac{1}{p_k \log^2 p_k}, \tag{4.1}$$

where the constant δ_0 is given by $\delta_0 = \sum_{k=1}^{r-1} G_k^{-1} - e \sum_{k=1}^{r-1} p_k^{-1}$. Let $x_0 = p_r = 88789$. By [10, Corollary 5.2], for $x \geq x_0$ we have

$$\pi(x) \geq \frac{x}{\log x} + \frac{x}{\log^2 x} + \frac{2x}{\log^3 x}. \tag{4.2}$$

Applying Equation (4.2) to Equation (3.2), we obtain

$$\sum_{k=r}^n \frac{1}{p_k \log p_k} = \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{p_k \log p_k} - \sum_{k=1}^{r-1} \frac{1}{p_k \log p_k} \geq \alpha_0 - \frac{1}{\log p_n} + \frac{3}{2 \log^4 p_n}$$

for $n \geq r$, where

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_0 = & - \sum_{k=1}^{r-1} \frac{1}{p_k \log p_k} + \int_2^{x_0} \pi(t) \left(\frac{1}{t^2 \log t} + \frac{1}{t^2 \log^2 t} \right) dt \\ & + \frac{1}{\log x_0} + \frac{1}{\log^2 x_0} + \frac{1}{\log^3 x_0} + \frac{1}{2 \log^4 x_0}. \end{aligned}$$

A direct computation shows that $\alpha_0 \geq 0.087676913224$. Hence

$$\sum_{k=r}^n \frac{1}{p_k \log p_k} \geq 0.087676913224 - \frac{1}{\log p_n}. \tag{4.3}$$

Similarly, we combine Equation (4.2) and Equation (3.3) to get

$$\sum_{k=r}^n \frac{1}{p_k \log^2 p_k} \geq 0.00384517884595949 - \frac{1}{2 \log^2 p_n}. \tag{4.4}$$

Now we apply Equation (4.3) and Equation (4.4) to Equation (4.1). Thus,

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k^{-1} > e \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{p_k} + \delta_0 + 0.0980588961e - \frac{e}{\log p_n} - \frac{2.7e}{2 \log^2 p_n}.$$

Since $\delta_0 > -1.1492179413$ and $e/\log x_0 + 2.7e/(2 \log^2 x_0) < 0.26683761711$, we obtain

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k^{-1} > e \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{p_k} - 1.14951.$$

Using [2, Proposition 7] and the definition of C'_n , we get the left-hand side inequality of Equation (1.4) for every $n \geq r$. A computer check shows that this inequality also holds for every integer n with $3 \leq n \leq r - 1$.

Next, we prove that the right-hand side inequality of Equation (1.4) holds for every integer $n \geq 6$. First let $n \geq s = 406\,161$. We use [4, Proposition 5.6] to see that

$$\sum_{k=1}^n G_k^{-1} < \alpha_1 + e \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{p_k} + e \sum_{k=s}^n \frac{1}{p_k \log p_k} + 6.83e \sum_{k=s}^n \frac{1}{p_k \log^2 p_k},$$

where $\alpha_1 = \sum_{k=1}^{s-1} G_k^{-1} - e \sum_{k=1}^{s-1} p_k^{-1}$. By Equation (3.4), we have

$$\sum_{k=s}^n \frac{1}{p_k \log p_k} \leq \sum_{p \in \mathbb{P}} \frac{1}{p \log p} - \sum_{k=1}^{s-1} \frac{1}{p_k \log p_k} \leq 0.064143634391656,$$

and from Equation (3.5) it follows that

$$\sum_{k=s}^n \frac{1}{p_k \log^2 p_k} \leq \sum_{p \in \mathbb{P}} \frac{1}{p \log^2 p} - \sum_{k=1}^{s-1} \frac{1}{p_k \log^2 p_k} \leq 0.002057210885594.$$

If we combine this with the fact that $\alpha_1 < -1.059057099768616$, we get

$$C'_n < e - \frac{0.8465}{\sum_{k=1}^n p_k^{-1}}.$$

By Dusart [9, Théorème 2], we have

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{p_k} < \log \log p_n + B + \frac{1}{10 \log^2 p_n} + \frac{4}{15 \log^3 p_n}. \tag{4.5}$$

Here B denotes the Mertens' constant and is defined by

$$B = \gamma + \sum_{p \in \mathbb{P}} \left(\log \left(1 - \frac{1}{p} \right) + \frac{1}{p} \right) = 0.2614972128476427837554268386 \dots,$$

where $\gamma = 0.57721\dots$ denotes the Euler–Mascheroni constant. Rosser and Schoenfeld showed [14, p. 69] that $p_n < n(\log n + \log \log n)$. Applying this inequality to Equation (4.5), we see that

$$\sum_{k=1}^n \frac{1}{p_k} < \log \log n + \log \left(1 + \frac{\log(\log n + \log \log n)}{\log n} \right) + B + \frac{1}{10 \log^2 p_n} + \frac{4}{15 \log^3 p_n}. \quad (4.6)$$

A simple calculation shows that the right-hand side of Equation (4.6) is less than $\log \log n + 0.454329$ which gives

$$C'_n < e - \frac{0.8465}{\log \log n + 0.454329}.$$

Now it suffices to apply the inequality

$$-\frac{0.8465}{\log \log n + 0.454329} < -\frac{0.71884}{\log \log n}$$

to complete the proof of the right-hand side inequality of Equation (1.4) for every integer $n \geq s$. For smaller values of n , we check the required inequality by direct computation. \square

Acknowledgements. We express our gratitude to the anonymous referee(s) for careful reading of the manuscript and giving the many valuable suggestions and corrections, which improved the presentation of the paper. We also greatly indebted to Prof. H. Cohen for a private conversation on the manuscript and helpful comments.

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